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ENVIRONMENTAL ENGINEERING UNDERGRADUATE DISSERTATION WORK DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

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ABSTRACT

The dissertation has been widely recognised as an important component of the engineering bachelor's degrees. However, undergraduates' lack of prior research exposure and acquisition of the necessary research skills can be exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic. This research analysed the influence of COVID-19 on the undergraduate dissertation of an Environmental Engineering programme at one university in the UK. A mixed-methods approach, a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods, was applied to understand the process of engineering students' dissertation work and their mental health during the pandemic. The results show that approximately 28.13% of the students thought the pandemic largely or very largely impacted their dissertations. In addition, 29.69% of the students thought COVID-19 had largely or very largely impacted their mental health. Notably, more female students (34.88%) considered that the pandemic had largely or very largely impacted their mental health. Around 24.14% - 37.50% of students with first or second grades thought COVID-19 had large or very large impacts on their dissertations. Nearly 50% of students with first grades and 37.5% of students with lower second grades considered the pandemic had largely or very largely impacted their mental health. The interviews indicated that the pandemic caused more anxiety, sleep disorders, and other mental health issues among students. This research sheds light on the challenges faced by Environmental Engineering undergraduates during the pandemic. In addition to academic support for engineering students, mental health is indispensable for them, particularly for girls and students with special educational needs, during the pandemic.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The dissertation or research project is an important component of the pedagogy for engineering undergraduate students [1]. Working for nearly one year, students are equipped with various skills, including collecting samples, analysing data, and writing reports. For some Engineering programmes, such as Environmental Engineering, most students are often involved with field sampling and laboratory work. Different from postgraduates, undergraduate students often have limited research experience before their dissertations. One of the critical changes of engineering students that are quickly required is to transfer from directed study in large classrooms to independent research under the advice of a supervisor. Most engineering undergraduates encounter enormous difficulties throughout changes from coursework learning to independent research. The inadequacy of research training and acquisition of required skills can be exacerbated by education disruption, such as the COVID-19 pandemic.

Studies on undergraduate dissertations indicate that students valued supervisors' support and the increased autonomy, but they also struggled with data collection and time management during the whole dissertation period [2]. Many students would like more supervision, and a survey suggested that around one-third of students are not satisfied with the supervision they obtain [3]. Although there are many studies on postgraduate dissertations, the lessons learned from these studies cannot directly transfer to undergraduate dissertations due to no or very limited research experience, lower research interest, and a shorter timeframe to complete the dissertation [4].

The COVID-19 pandemic has produced an unprecedented disruption of global education. It is estimated that around 1.6 billion learners have been affected globally [5]. Over 94% of the world's students have been impacted by the closures of universities and other learning spaces. Restrictive movement and social distancing policies have brought massive disturbances to the traditional educational system. Clearly, new educational and assessment strategies are required during the pandemic, even after.

Remote and online learning, or hybrid education in certain periods or some areas have become a remedy for this unprecedented COVID-19 pandemic. However, the rapid change from traditional face-to-face education to online education is huge challenge for both teachers and students, called "Crisis distance education" [6]. Universities and teachers have taken "Education in Emergency" strategies through numerous online platforms, for example, Blackboard, Microsoft Teams, Google Classroom, and others. Teachers and students have to adapt to the new technology and changes quickly, while their adaptation needs to be supported and gauged carefully. Researchers have highlighted the large challenges for the education sector during the pandemic, for example, the poor online education infrastructure, teachers' inadequate exposure to online instruction, and non-conducive home environment for learning [5].

Notably, university students' mental health has received increasing attention. In this research, I adopted the World Health Organization definition "*Mental health is a state*

of well-being in which an individual realizes his or her own abilities, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and is able to make a contribution to his or her community” [7]. Having good mental health means that students are able to think, feel, and act the way that the students want and need to live their lives; students with poor mental health might find it difficult, or even impossible, to cope with the way they regularly think, feel and act. Mental illness can largely influence students’ motivation, concentration, and social communication, which are all important factors for students’ success. Worse, the COVID-19 pandemic can exacerbate the mental health damage to this vulnerable group. A recent review reported the mental health damages by the pandemic, for example, the anxiety of virus infection, frustration during quarantine and lockdown period, depression, sleep disorder, stigma, and others [8].

However, the impact of the COVID-19 on Engineering students’ dissertation has not yet been explored. Based on the “Crisis distance education” theory [6], this study used a mixed-methods approach (questionnaire and interview) to analyse Environmental Engineering students’ dissertations during the pandemic. The overall research question is “How did the COVID-19 impact environmental engineering students’ dissertation work and mental health”. The main aims of the research are to 1) evaluate the impact of COVID-19 on students’ dissertation; and 2) estimate the influence of COVID-19 on students’ mental health. The findings will be useful for universities and instructors to understand students’ challenges during conducting dissertation in the COVID-19 pandemic. The findings will have immediate implications for developing new measures to support students during conducting dissertations in the ongoing pandemic and future crisis periods in Europe and other regions.

2 METHODOLOGY

This research applied a mixed-methods approach, a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods [9]. An online questionnaire survey was carried out to understand engineering students’ experiences of conducting dissertations. The questionnaire is composed of 10 questions, including students’ opinions of the impact of COVID-19 on their dissertation and mental health. Students’ backgrounds, including gender and academic grades (First, Upper Second, Lower Second, Third, and Fail), were also surveyed.

The semi-standardized interviews were performed to produce a micro-level view of students’ experience of conducting dissertations. In total, 12 students were recruited via purposeful and voluntary sampling. Interviews were recorded and transcribed for thematic analysis [9].

This research is subject to ethical review in conformity with the standards established by the Research Ethics Committee, University of Reading, and has been allowed to proceed.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Questionnaire results

In total, 64 Environmental Engineering students participated in the survey, including 21 male and 43 female students. In terms of their opinions of the impact of COVID-19 on dissertations, less than half of students (43.75%) thought there was a small impact of COVID-19 on their dissertations, but 28.13% of students thought there were large or very large impacts on their dissertations (*Figure 1*). In general, male and female students shared similar opinions of the impact of COVID-19 on their dissertation projects. Notably, more female students (13.95%) than male students (9.52%) considered the pandemic had very largely impacted their dissertations.

Figure 1. How has the COVID-19 pandemic affected your dissertation project? (A) is male and (B) is female students.

Regarding students' opinions of the impact of COVID-19 on their mental health, 53.13% of the participants thought the COVID-19 had small or very small impacts on their mental health, while 29.69% of the students thought their mental health had been largely or very largely impacted by COVID-19. It is worth mentioning that more female students (34.88%) than male students (19.04%) considered that their mental health had been largely or very largely impacted by the pandemic (*Figure 2*).

Figure 2. How has the COVID-19 pandemic affected your mental health? (A) is male and (B) is female students.

Students with different grades had various opinions of the impact of COVID-19 on their dissertations. Obviously, 24.14% - 37.50% of students with the first or second grades thought COVID-19 had large or very large impacts on their dissertations (*Figure 3*). However, students with the third or fail grades only thought small or very small impacts of COVID-19 on their dissertations.

Figure 3. Students' opinions of the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on their dissertation versus students' grades.

There are also differences in students' opinion of the impact of COVID-19 on their mental health between students with various grades (Figure 4). Nearly 50% of students with the first grades and 37.5% of students with lower second grades considered the pandemic had very largely or largely impacted their mental health. All students with the third grade thought COVID-19 had a large impact on their mental health, but the student with fail considered only small or very small impact of the pandemic on their mental health.

Figure 4. Students' opinions of the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on their mental health versus students' grades.

3.2 Interview results

We have interviewed 12 students about their study and research experience when doing the dissertation projects. Obviously, students emphasized the large impact of COVID-19 on their dissertations. Several students elaborated on their mental health issues, although sometimes they have not yet realized them.

1) A difficult journey during the pandemic

Most students felt it very difficult to do the dissertation due to various restrictions by pandemic, and the most obvious one is the challenges to do field sampling.

However, many Environmental Engineering students would like to do fieldwork. One student clearly commented:

I prefer to go sampling in the field.

Without sufficient research training, many students felt dissertation is difficult. One student exemplified this by the struggling of data analysis:

I think it is quite difficult. I do not really know how to analyse the data.

One student described a desperate situation as follows:

I feel it was extremely hard to do a dissertation. I felt like I was going to burn out.

2) Large mental health damage to some students

In the interviews, some students addressed apparent mental health issues, such as anxiety commented by one student as follows:

During the year, I am often very anxious and stressed because there's still so much knowledge I don't know, so much analysis I have not done, and I get very worried about the results.

Sleep disorder was also mentioned by some students. They found it very difficult to fall asleep and wake up much earlier than they normally do, called insomnia. For example, one student commented:

I sleep less than other people. I sleep six or five hours a day, maybe even less. I just cannot sleep.

4 DISCUSSION

4.1 More academic support for engineering students' dissertations during the pandemic

“Crisis distance education” theory [6] emphasized the suddenness, imposition, and medical emergencies for the education sector during the pandemic. The current survey and interview results are in good agreement with the theory. During the pandemic, students generally felt more difficult to complete the dissertations, for example, restriction to field for collecting first-hand data and struggles with data analysis which were emphasized by several interviewees. Previous studies have confirmed the importance of supervisors' support and students' autonomy in such a difficult time [10]. To help students conduct dissertation research, students in this researched University have been provided with more secondary data analysis training, such as collecting and analysing data from Environmental Agency. Instead of field and laboratory work, some students adopted online questionnaires and interview projects, and more training on data collection and analysis of surveys and interviews was also provided. The University also introduced the Circumstances Impact Process (CIP) to minimise any anxiety and academic disadvantage caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, as part of a series of measures to support students in the COVID-19 pandemic. Despite such support, some students still experience challenges when conducting dissertation projects in this pandemic, as shown in Figures 1-4.

In particular, supervisors need to offer clear and directed advice, inspire and support students' confidence, and foster student independence and development. To obtain secondary data for conducting dissertations, supervisors need to help students explore more secondary data sources. Some analyses of secondary data, for example, statistical analysis and modelling, are usually not taught before, and thus more supports are also needed from supervisors.

According to the survey results (Figure 2), more girls (34.88%) than boys (19.04%) thought the pandemic had largely or very largely affected their mental health. Because 67.19% of respondents are girls, the resurvey results may be biased. However, it at least indicates that more support is needed for female students to prevent and alleviate their mental health issues during the pandemic. In addition, students with special educational needs suffered more challenges in the pandemic. Therefore, there is a requirement for providing more time and resources to explore the best alternatives for the special educational needs of these students.

4.2 Support engineering students' mental health during the pandemic

It is important to check the well-being of students during the pandemic and effective measures are taken to minimise the damage of pandemic on students' study and their health, including mental health. This survey showed that 29.69% of the students thought COVID-19 had largely or very largely impacted their mental health and the proportion is even higher for girls (34.88%) (Figure 2). Most students mentioned that they have tried to deal with anxiety, sleep disorder, and other mental health issues, mainly by distracting themselves by entertaining, such as watching videos or doing other tasks. The university provides the tele-counselling, but the students with mental health issues had rarely or never used the counselling services in the COVID-19 pandemic. Some researchers have ascribed it to not being perceived as severe enough to seek professional counselling, not comfortable engaging with unfamiliar people, and little trust in the counselling services [11].

Clearly, more vigilance and support are needed to help these students, especially those are suffering some mental health damages while they may have not yet realized the impacts and consequences. Our interviews suggest that students preferred self-management. This should be encouraged, but it is clearly insufficient. With the development of telehealth applications and digital technologies, it is promising to enable more self-management of mental health problems. More importantly, students should take adaptive coping, for example, acceptance and proactive behaviours. It is also important to identify students' coping behaviour for informing the support systems. For instance, the participatory models of intervention development can be applied. By engaging with the target individuals, psychologists can adapt interventional programs to students' specific contexts.

4.3 Limitation and future research

Similar to most studies, the results of the current research should be applied in light of the study limitations. This study can be biased by the research sample sizes and the imbalanced gender ratio of the survey participants. However, it is convinced that students' difficulties and mental health issues during the pandemic illustrated in the current study have broader relevance throughout engineering education. Future work

should expand the sample size and recruit more engineering students to the study. Further exploration of students' difficulties in each stage of conducting dissertations (selecting research topics, designing research methods, collecting and analysing data, and writing) is also warranted.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The unprecedented COVID-19 pandemic has brought massive negative impacts on higher education. The questionnaire results indicated approximately 28.13% of the students thought the pandemic had largely or very largely impacted their dissertations and 29.69% of the students thought COVID-19 has largely or very largely impacted their mental health. The interviews also suggested the large mental health damages, for example, anxiety and sleep disorder, during the pandemic. The findings of this study highlight the importance of developing interventions and preventive strategies to address the difficulties and mental health of engineering students.

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